

Exploration of Biosurfactant-Producing Microorganisms from Hydrocarbon-Contaminated Sites

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Abstract:

Biosurfactants are eco-friendly surface-active molecules with varied industrial applications. In this study, thirteen bacterial isolates from contaminated soil were screened for biosurfactant production using drop collapse, oil displacement and emulsification index (E24) assays. Amongst the total isolates GS-3 showed the highest activity. Morphological and biochemical characterization identified GS-3 as *Bacillus* spp. Biosurfactant production was carried out using 1% diesel as a carbon source. The biosurfactant was extracted by acid precipitation and solvent extraction. CTAB assay confirmed its anionic nature. The results reveal that GS-3 is a promising candidate for biosurfactant production with potential applications in bioremediation.

Introduction:

Biosurfactants are amphiphilic compounds produced by microorganisms, possessing both hydrophilic and hydrophobic moieties. They have gained attention due to their structural diversity, low toxicity, high biodegradability, environmental compatibility, and low critical micelle concentration (CMC) (Saravanan & Vijaykumar, 2015). These properties make them promising alternatives to synthetic surfactants in industries such as food, agriculture, pharmaceuticals, cosmetics, and petroleum. However, their large-scale application is limited by high production costs (Vandana & Singh, 2018).

Various microorganisms, including *Pseudomonas*, *Bacillus*, *Corynebacterium*, *Acinetobacter*, and yeasts like *Candida* and *Pseudozyma*, are known to produce biosurfactants. These compounds reduce surface and interfacial tension and enhance emulsification, improving the bioavailability of

hydrophobic substrates (Khamis *et al.*, 2003). Based on molecular weight, biosurfactants are classified into low- and high-molecular-weight types (Rosenberg & Ron, 1999). Low-molecular-weight biosurfactants, such as glycolipids and lipopeptides, are effective in reducing surface tension, while high-molecular-weight types stabilize emulsions (Shoeb *et al.*, 2013).

Major classes include glycolipids (rhamnolipids, sophorolipids, trehalolipids), lipopeptides (surfactin, lichenysin), and lipid-based compounds. Rhamnolipids from *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and sophorolipids from yeasts are widely studied for their surface activity, while surfactin from *Bacillus subtilis* shows strong antimicrobial properties (Gautam & Tyagi, 2006; McInerney *et al.*, 1990; Vandana & Singh, 2018).

Biosurfactant production depends on nutritional and environmental factors, with carbon sources such as oils, hydrocarbons, and industrial wastes playing a key role. Media like MSM,

HSM, LB, and NB are commonly used. Screening involves qualitative assays such as drop collapse, oil displacement, emulsification index, haemolysis, and CTAB tests, while quantitative and analytical methods include DNS, anthrone, TLC, GC, HPLC, and FTIR (Garcia & Reyes, 2016). Recovery is achieved through centrifugation, filtration, solvent extraction, and precipitation methods (Sen & Swaminathan, 2005).

Biosurfactants have diverse applications as emulsifiers and stabilizers in food, eco-friendly agents in cosmetics and detergents, and enhancers of soil quality in agriculture. They also possess antimicrobial, antiviral, and anticancer properties for pharmaceutical use. In the petroleum sector, they play a vital role in enhanced oil recovery (MEOR) and bioremediation by reducing interfacial tension and increasing pollutant bioavailability (Wu *et al.*, 2022). Current research focuses on improving production efficiency and reducing costs using agro-industrial wastes and genetic approaches (Leonie *et al.*, 2022).

Materials and Methods:

Sample Collection:

For isolation of biosurfactant producing bacteria, two soil samples, the petrol pump soil sample (PS) and garage soil sample (GS) were collected stored at 4°C for further analysis.

Isolation of biosurfactant producing organism:

The soil samples were first serially diluted and plated by spread plate method on nutrient agar plates and incubated at 37°C for 24 hours. 1% Diesel was added to this medium as a source of carbon (Jayshree, *et al.*, 2011). Isolates were preserved at 4°C for further use.

Screening of biosurfactant producing organism:

Qualitative tests for biosurfactant detection:

It's essential to emphasize that the distinguishing factor between biosurfactants and

bioemulsifiers lies in their ability to lower surface and interfacial tension. This fundamental difference plays a crucial role in screening and identifying them from microbial culture broths accurately. Therefore, screening methods focusing on reducing surface tension are designed to exclude bioemulsifiers producers while selecting biosurfactant producers (Uzoigwe, *et al.*, 2015).

Selected isolates were inoculated into a nutrient broth containing 1% diesel fraction as source of carbon and incubated at 37°C at 200 Rpm for 7 days. The cultures were centrifuged 8000 rpm for 10 min and the supernatant were used for detection of biosurfactant production. Biosurfactant produced by the selected was detected by performing following tests.

Drop Collapse Test:

The drop collapse test proves highly efficient in identifying the biosurfactant in the given sample. The test involves addition of a drop of cell-free supernatant on a hydrophobic phase i.e. engine oil on a glass slide. Negative control was also set using distilled water along with the sample (Samsu, *et al.*, 2020).

Oil Displacement Test:

This technique is performed by adding 15 ml of distilled water into a petri dish lid. 1ml of engine oil was placed in this plate and 0.1 ml of sample of cell free supernatant was pipetted on this hydrophobic phase. The plates were left for 30 seconds for biosurfactant to form clear zone. Diameter was measured for each sample Positive and negative control was also maintained. (Jayshree, *et al.*, 2011)

Emulsification Index (E₂₄):

The assessment of biosurfactant emulsification towards engine oil was conducted following the Cooper & Goldenberg method. According to the method, 2ml of engine oil is added into a test tube and equal volume of cell-free supernatant added into the test tube. The

tubes were vortexed for 2 minutes and kept for incubation overnight at room temperature. Positive and negative control was also maintained along with the sample tubes. Later, the height of

emulsion and total height of the sample was noted down. The emulsification Index (E_{24}) was calculated by using formula:

$$\text{Emulsification index} = \frac{(\text{Height of the emulsion layer}) \times 100}{\text{Total height of sample}} \quad (\text{Jayshree, et al., 2011})$$

Cetyl trimethylammonium bromide (CTAB) Agar Assay:

In this procedure CTAB agar plates are prepared and 2 wells of 6.5 mm diameter are plunged on the CTAB agar plate. 150 μ l (0.15 ml) of cell free supernatant was loaded in each well and plates were incubated at 37°C for 48 hours. Diameter of halo was measured and compared with positive and negative control. (Rani, et al., 2020)

From the above tests, GS 3 was selected for the biosurfactant production due to its excellent results compared to other samples.

Production of biosurfactants using selected isolates:

Production of biosurfactant was carried out in 1 litre nutrient medium with 1% diesel as carbon source. GS-3 culture was inoculated into the medium and incubated 37°C for 48 hours at 200 rpm (Samsu, et al., 2020). Production of biosurfactants was identified by qualitative tests of biosurfactants.

Extraction of Biosurfactants:

Extraction of biosurfactants was carried out by acid precipitation method. The production medium was centrifuged at 10000 rpm for 10 minutes and supernatant was collected and acidified with 2N HCL until pH 2.0 & kept overnight at 4°C. The precipitate obtained was subjected to further centrifuged at 1000 rpm for 10 minutes, supernatant was removed and the pellets was subjected to solvent extraction with methanol; equal volume of methanol added to the

acid extracted biosurfactant, agitated vigorously and centrifuged at 8000 rpm for 10 minutes. The tubes were kept at 50 °c for evaporation (Smyth, et al., 2010; Salleh et al., 2011).

Cytotoxicity Assay:

Cytotoxicity assay of biosurfactant is important because of their wide spread applications in cosmetic as well as in food Industries. In this assay, 5gm goat liver was macerated into phosphate buffer (pH7). Absorbance of the cell suspension was measured at 575 nm and optical density was adjusted to 1. Positive control was prepared using 1ml of suspension HgCl₂ each and negative control consist of cell suspension. Biosurfactant was then serially diluted 25-100 percent using phosphate buffer. Test was carried out incubating 1ml of crude biosurfactant with 0.5 ml of goat liver cell suspension at 37°C for 2 hours. Following the incubation period, 500 μ l of the sample was mixed with 500 μ l of trypan blue dye solution (0.02%) in an Eppendorf tube. The mixture was then incubated for 10 minutes. Subsequently, approximately 100 μ l of the incubated sample was mounted on a Neubauer chamber and observed under a microscope at 40x magnification. (Pethkar, et al., 2012). The total number of viable and dead cells were counted, and the percentage of viable cells was calculated using a specific formula

$$\% \text{ of viable cells} = \frac{\text{Number of viable cells} \times 100}{\text{Total number of cells}}$$

Results and Discussion:

Isolation and Characterization:

A total 13 isolates were obtained from the collected samples, 6 from petrol pump soil sample and 7 from garage soil sample on medium containing 1% diesel. Petrol pump soil sample colonies were labelled as PS-1, PS-2, PS-6 and Garage soil sample colonies were labelled as GS-1, GS-2...GS-7.

Screening of biosurfactant producing organism:

Qualitative tests for detection of biosurfactant:

Thirteen isolates were screened for biosurfactant production using emulsification index (%E24), oil displacement, and drop collapse tests. Isolate PS-1 showed minimal activity, with no significant interfacial tension reduction and low emulsification. In contrast, GS-3 exhibited the highest biosurfactant potential, showing maximum activity in all assays (Fig 1, Fig: 2).

Fig: 1 (a) Drop collapse test; (b) Oil Displacement test; (c) Emulsification index

Figure 2 (a) Drop collapse results of GS sample

(b) emulsification results of GS sample

Chioma, *et al.*, (2013) reported that isolates X2 and X3 from automobile-contaminated soils showed maximum oil displacement activity with clearance zones of 11 mm and 7 mm. Similarly, Jaysree *et al.*, (2020) observed the highest emulsification indices of 20% and 30% in isolates W1 and S1 from artificial pond samples.

Cetyl Trimethylammonium Bromide (CTAB)

Agar Assay:

The CTAB agar assay was performed to detect the production of anionic biosurfactants. In this method, the cationic surfactant

cetyltrimethylammonium bromide (CTAB) forms a complex with anionic biosurfactants such as rhamnolipids in the presence of methylene blue, resulting in the formation of a visible zone of clearance. The potential isolate GS-3 was evaluated using this assay, and biosurfactant production was confirmed by the appearance of a clear zone on CTAB agar plates (Fig:3). Menon *et al.*, (2025), also confirmed the biosurfactant production using CTAB agar method and reported that isolates S1, S2,S3, W2, W9, A9 showed the maximum biosurfactant production.

Morphological and biochemical characterization of isolate GS-3:

Table: 1 Colony characteristics and biochemical characteristics of GS-3

Sr. No	Characters	GS-3
1.	Size	Pin-point
2.	Shape	Irregular
3.	Colour	Off-White
4.	Margin	Undulate
5.	Elevation	Raised
6.	Consistency	Butyrous
7.	Opacity	Opaque
8.	Surface	Smooth
9.	Grams Nature	Positive Short rods
10.	Indole Test	Negative
11.	Methyl Red	Positive
12.	Voges-Proskauer test (VP)	Negative
13.	Citrate Utilization Test	Positive
14.	Glucose Fermentation	Positive
15.	Mannitol Fermentation	Positive
16.	Catalase Test	Positive
17.	Nitrate Reduction	Positive

GS-3 was characterized by morphological and biochemical analyses and identified as Gram-positive rods, which preliminarily identified as *Bacillus spp.* (Table 1; Fig: 4).

Fig:1. CTAB Assay of GS-3

Fig: 2. GS-3 isolate

Dwivedi *et al.*, (2018) conducted morphological and biochemical characterization of isolate Alk-35, selected from 49 strains obtained from petrol pump-contaminated soil. Based on these analyses, the isolate was

preliminarily identified as *Corynebacterium* spp. and was further evaluated for its biosurfactant-producing potential.

Production and extraction of the biosurfactant:

Biosurfactant production by GS-3 was carried out in 1 L medium containing 1% diesel and incubated at 37°C for 48 h at 200 rpm. Production was confirmed by qualitative assays, with turbidity indicating active growth and metabolism. The biosurfactant was subsequently extracted from the cell-free supernatant using acid precipitation followed by solvent extraction. Partial purification yielded an off-white powder, which was used for further analysis

Sumathi and Yogananth (2016) isolated biosurfactant-producing microorganisms from oil-contaminated marine sediment samples. The biosurfactant was extracted using the acid precipitation method, and preliminary characterization by thin-layer chromatography (TLC) identified it as a rhamnolipid.

Cytotoxicity Assay:

Total and non-viable cells were counted, and the percentage of viable cells was calculated using standard methods, with total cell count obtained from the negative control. Cytotoxicity analysis of the GS-3 biosurfactant (Fig:5) indicated its effect on goat cell suspension, suggesting its potential application in bioremediation of inanimate environments.

Fig: 5. Cytotoxicity analysis of isolate GS-3

Conclusion:

This study demonstrated successful isolation, screening, production and characterization of a biosurfactant producing bacteria, GS-3 from oil contaminated soil environments. Morphological and biochemical analysis of the isolate preliminarily identified it as *Bacillus* spp. The isolate showed significant biosurfactant producing potential, confirmed by qualitative assays viz. drop collapse, oil displacement, emulsification index and CTAB agar test. Biosurfactant production effectively achieved using diesel as a carbon source, followed by successful extraction of it. Preliminary characterization and cytotoxicity analysis suggest that the biosurfactant possess functional properties suitable for environmental applications. Overall the findings highlight the potential of GS-3 derived biosurfactant as an eco-friendly alternative for application like hydrocarbon degradation and bioremediation. Further studies focusing on structural characterization, optimization of production and scale-up processes for enhanced industrial application.

References:

1. Chioma, O., Ogechukwu, M., Bright, O., Simon, O. & Chinyere, A. (2013). Isolation and Characterization of Biosurfactants Producing Bacteria from Oil Polluted Soil. *Journal of Natural Sciences Research*, 3, 119-122.
2. Dwivedi, A., Kumar, A. & Bhat, J. (2019). Production and Characterization of Biosurfactant from *Corynebacterium* Species and Its Effect on the Growth of Petroleum Degrading Bacteria. *Microbiology*. 88. 87-93. DOI: [10.1134/S002626171901003X](https://doi.org/10.1134/S002626171901003X)
3. Gautam, K. & Tyagi, V. K. (2006). Microbial Surfactants: a review. *Journal of*

- Oleo Science, 55(4), 155–166.
<https://doi.org/10.5650/jos.55.155>
4. García-Reyes, S. & Yañez-Ocampo, G. (2016). Microbial Biosurfactants: Methods for Their Isolation And Characterization. *J Microbiol Biotech Food Sci.* 6 (1) 641-648
5. [doi: 10.15414/jmbfs.2016.6.1.641-648](https://doi.org/10.15414/jmbfs.2016.6.1.641-648)
 6. Jaysree, R.C., Basu, S., Singh, P.P., Ghosal, T., Patra, P.A., Keerthi, Y. & Rajendran, N. (2011). Isolation of biosurfactant producing bacteria from environmental samples. *Pharmacologyonline*, 3, 1427-1433.
 7. Khamis, N., Abdul Rahim, A., Ibrahim, N.A. & Abdul Kadir, P. Z. (2020). Characterization of biosurfactant production by indigenous bacteria from Sungai Dungun estuary, Trengganu by surface activity and emulsification test. *IOP Conf. Series: Earth and Environmental Science* 596. 012003. [doi:10.1088/1755-1315/596/1/012003](https://doi.org/10.1088/1755-1315/596/1/012003)
 8. Sarubbo, L. A.; Silva, M. da G. C.; Durval, I. J. B.; Bezerra, K. G. O.; Ribeiro, B. G.; Silva, I. A.; Twigg, M. S.; Banat, I. M. (2022). Biosurfactants: Production, Properties, Applications, Trends, and General Perspectives. *Biochem Eng. J.* 2022, 181, 108377, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bej.2022.108377>
 9. McNerney, M. J., Javaheri, M., & Nagle, D. P., Jr (1990). Properties of the biosurfactant produced by *Bacillus licheniformis* strain JF-2. *Journal of industrial microbiology*, 5(2-3), 95–101.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/BF01573858>
 10. Menon, S., Mishra, A., Krishnan, J., Ravindran, A K., Sneha, P.U. and Kushbu, R. (2025)
 11. Production and characterization of biosurfactant from novel strains isolated from environmental samples. *Journal of Applied Biology & Biotechnology*.13(4), 136-145.
[DOI: 10.7324/JABB.2025.221419](https://doi.org/10.7324/JABB.2025.221419)
 12. Pethkar, A., Lele, P., Patil, S. N., Ramdasi, A., & Kalmani, S. (2012). Standardization of a rapid and inexpensive in-vitro cytotoxicity assay. *Journal of Environmental Research and Development*, 6(3A), 645-652.
 13. Rani, M., Weadge, J. T., & Jabaji, S. (2020). Isolation and characterization of Biosurfactant-Producing bacteria from oil well batteries with antimicrobial activities against Food-Borne and plant pathogens. *Frontiers in Microbiology*, 11.
<https://doi.org/10.3389/fmicb.2020.00064>
 14. Rosenberg, E., & Ron, E. Z. (1999). High- and low-molecular-mass microbial surfactants. *Applied microbiology and biotechnology*, 52(2), 154–162.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s002530051502>
 15. Salleh, S. M., Noh, N. A. M. And Yahya, A. R. M. (2011). Comparative study: Different recovery techniques of rhamnolipid produced by *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* USMAR-2. In: *International Conference on Biotechnology and Environment Management IPCBEE.*, 18, 432-562.
 16. Samsu, Z. A., Jeffry, F. N., Azizan, W. N. A. N. W. A.R. (2020). Isolation and screening of potential biosurfactant-producing bacteria from used engine oil-contaminated soil. *Materials Today: Proceedings*. 31 (1), A67-A71.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matpr.2020.12.438>
 17. Sen, R., & Swaminathan, T. (2005). Characterization of concentration and purification parameters and operating conditions for the small-scale recovery of surfactin. *Process Biochemistry*, 40(9), 2953–2958.

- <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procbio.2005.01.014>
18. Shoeb, E., Akhlaq, F., Badar, U., Akhter, J., & Imtiaz, S. (2013). Classification and Industrial Applications Of Biosurfactants. *Academic Rese. Int.*4(3) 243-252.
 19. Smyth, T. J., Perfumo, A., McClean, S., Marchant, R., & Banat, Í. M. (2010). Isolation and analysis of lipopeptides and high molecular weight biosurfactants. In *Springer eBooks* (pp. 3687–3704). https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-540-77587-4_290
 20. Sumathi, Raja & Nagarajan, Yogananth. (2016). Isolation and identification of Biosurfactant producing *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* from marine sediment samples and its Antimicrobial Properties. *Int. J. Adv. Res. Biol. Sci.*3(12) 200-212. DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.22192/ijarbs.2016.03.12.029>
 21. Uzoigwe C, Burgess JG, Ennis CJ and Rahman PKSM (2015) Bioemulsifiers are not biosurfactants and require different screening approaches. *Front. Microbiol.* 6:245. doi: [10.3389/fmicb.2015.00245](https://doi.org/10.3389/fmicb.2015.00245)
 22. Vandana, P., & Singh, D. (2018). Review on Biosurfactant Production and its Application. *International Journal of Current Microbiology and Applied Sciences*, 7(08), 4228–4241. <https://doi.org/10.20546/ijcmas.2018.708.443>
 23. Vijayakumar, S., & Saravanan, V. (2015). Biosurfactants-Types, Sources and Applications. *Journal of Microbiology*, 10(5), 181–192. <https://doi.org/10.3923/jm.2015.181.192>
 24. Wu, B., Xiu, J., Li Yu., Huang, L & Ma, Y. (2022). Biosurfactant production by *Bacillus subtilis* SL and its potential for enhanced oil recovery in low permeability reservoirs. *Scientific Reports* | (2022) 12:7785 | <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-022-12025-7>